

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES
SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

OPTIMIZATION AND VERIFICATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR ANALYSIS OF ASSAY OF CHLORPROMAZINE HCL

K. Monika^{*1}, P. Chandru^{*1}, D. Jayashree^{*1}, Deepa. G^{*2}Gokulan. P.D^{*3},
SenthilKumar. K.L^{*4}

¹ B.Pharm Students, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College Of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.

² Professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College Of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.

³ Associate Professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College Of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.

⁴ Principal, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College Of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.

Abstract:

This study presents the development and validation of a high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method for analysis of chlorpromazine HCl. The chromatography condition were optimized, and the method was validated for system suitability, specificity, precision, linearity, accuracy. Result indicate that the developed HPLC method is suitable for accurate quantification of Chlorpromazine hl in pharmaceutical formulation. This research contributes to ensuring the quality and reliability of chlorpromazine HCl analysis in pharmaceutical laboratories.

Keywords: Chlorpromazine Hcl, RP-HPMC, Chromatogram, Acetonitrile

Corresponding author:**K. Monika.,***B.Pharm Students,**Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College Of Pharmacy,**Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.*

QR code

Please cite this article in press K. Monika et al., *Optimization And Verification Of RP-HPLC Method For Analysis Of Assay Of Chlorpromazine Hcl.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12 (01).

1. INTRODUCTION:

Analytical chemistry may be defined as “science and art of determining the composition of materials in terms of elements or compounds contained”. HPLC is a separation technique based on stationary phase and liquid mobile phase. Separation achieved by partition, adsorption, or ion exchange process, depending upon size of stationary phases used. To quantify and evaluate the products an analytical methods need to be validated. validation is a basic requirement to ensure quality and reliability of results for all analytical application. Validation is defined by different agencies EC, FDA, WHO.

Figure 1 : Structure of chlorpromazine HCL

Molecular formula: C₁₇H₁₉ClN₂S, Molecular weight: 318.86 g/mol, IUPAC name: 3-(2-chloro-10H-phenothiazin-10-yl)-N,N-dimethylpropan-1-amine. Uses: Treatment for schizophrenia, mania and psychosis.

Instrumental methods of Chemical analysis:

Instrumental method is an exciting and fascinating part of chemical analysis that interacts with all areas of chemistry and with many other areas of pure and applied sciences. Analytical instrumentation plays an important role in the production and evaluation of new products and in the protection of consumers and environment. This instrumentation provides lower detection limits required to assure safe foods, drugs, and water air. Instrumental methods are widely used by Analytical chemists to save time, to avoid chemical separation and to obtain increased accuracy.

Most instrumental techniques fit into one of the four principle areas. For convenience and better understanding introduction is divided into three parts,

- A) Spectroscopy
- B) Chromatography
- C) Validation

Other chapters such as objectives, methodology, results, discussion, and conclusion have been divided into two parts,

- A) UV Spectrophotometry

- B) High Performance Liquid Chromatography

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Materials:

Chlorpromazine HCL Active pharmaceutical ingredient was obtained from pharma labs. Analytical balance, pH meter, vacuum oven, column

Reagents and chemicals:

Dibasic sodium phosphate heptahydrate, ortho phosphate acid, acetonitrile, WFI (water).

METHODOLOGY:

PREPARATION OF SOLUTIONS:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Prepare a mixture of **Buffer and Acetonitrile** as 30:70. Filter and degas. For 3000ml of mobile phase mix 900 of Buffer and 2100mL of Acetonitrile, and sonicated it for degas.

Preparation of Buffer:

Prepare a mixture of 2.68g of dibasic Ammonium hydrogen phosphate in 1000mL water. Adjust the pH of 3.0 using Ortho phosphoric acid and make the volume with water.

Preparation of Diluent:

Use mobile phase as a diluent.

Preparation of Standard solution:

Weigh accurately about 10.0 mg of Chlorpromazine reference / working standard into a 100mL volumetric flask, dissolve and make up to the mark with mobile phase. (Prepare a 0.1mg/mL of Chlorpromazine in mobile phase).

Preparation of Sample solution:

Weigh accurately about 10.0mg of Chlorpromazine sample into a 100mL volumetric flask, dissolve and make up to the mark with mobile phase. (Prepare a 0.1mg/mL of Chlorpromazine in mobile phase)

Chromatographic condition:

Column	Waters, 250mm x 4.6mm, 5µm diameter
Detector	UV, 254 nm
Flow rate	1.0mL/min
Injection volume	10µL
Column oven temperature	25 °C
	15 minutes
Auto sample temperature	5°C

III. METHOD OF ANALYSIS:

System suitability:

To verify that the analytical system is working properly and can give accurate and precise results, the system suitability parameters are to be set.

Specificity:

Specificity is the ability of analytical method to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of component that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products and matrix components.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple sampling of homogeneous sample. The precision of analytical method is usually expressed as the standard deviation or relative standard deviation (Coefficient of variation) of series of measurements.

- System Precision
- Method Precision

Linearity:

The Linearity of an analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are directly, or by a well-

defined mathematical transformation, proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range.

Prepare the blank and standard solutions as described in the methodology section. Perform the linearity for Chlorpromazine standard in the range of 50% to 150% of working standard concentration

Accuracy:

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value (Standard value). Prepare the Chlorpromazine standard at 50%, 100%, and 150% of working concentration in triplicate. Analyse this sample in triplicate for each level. From the results, calculate the mg of Chlorpromazine for each level. Prepare the blank, standard solution and standard solutions as described in the methodology section.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A) System suitability:

Chromatogram for system suitability

Result:

Table:-1 Results parameter.

S.No	Acceptance Criteria	Result
1	Tailing factor for Chlorpromazine peak should be not more than 2.0	1.17
2	Theoretical plates for Chlorpromazine peak in standard Solution should be more than 2000	5300
3	RSD for Chlorpromazine peak in standard solution should not be more than 1.0%	0.02%

for System

B) Specificity:**Chromatogram for specificity**

Result:

S.No	Acceptance Criteria	Result
1	There should be no interfering peak in the chromatogram at the retention time corresponding to the peak of Chlorpromazine.	Complies

Table 2: Result of Specificity parameter

C) Precision**SYSTEM PRECISION**

Result:

Table 3: Result of specific suitability parameter

S.No	Acceptance Criteria	Results
1	The RSD of the Retention time for Chlorpromazine peak obtained from 6 injections of standard solutions should be NMT 1.0%	0.02%
2	The RSD of the Area response for Chlorpromazine peak obtained from 6 injections of standard solutions should be NMT 1.0%	0.27%

METHOD PRECISION

Result:

S.NO	ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA	RESULT
1	The results should be within the specification limit.	Complies
2	The RSD calculated on 6 determinations for Chlorpromazine content should be NMT 2.0%	1.756%

Table 4: Result of system parameter

D) Linearity

Slope	3306849.10929
Intercept	38195.0000
% Intercept	1.15
Correlation Co-efficient	0.9999
Regression Correlation Co-efficient(r^2)	0.9999

Result:

Table 5: Result of system parameter

S.No	Acceptance Criteria	Result
1	CorrelationCoefficientandRegressionCoefficientshouldbeNLTO.998.	0.9999
2	%Y intercept should be $\pm 2\%$ at100% concentration level.	1.15%

E) Accuracy**Result:**

Table 6: Result of specific suitability parameter

S.NO	ACCEPTANCECRITERIA	%RECOVERY	RESULT
1	Accuracy level 50%(80-120%)	%Recovery	99.57
2	Accuracy level 100%(80-120%)	%Recovery	99.68
3	Accuracy level 150%(80-120%)	%Recovery	99.75

V.CONCLUSION:

A simple ,rapid, specific and economic chromatographic method have been developed for the assay of Chlorpromazine by HPLC. The HPLC determination was achieved with the mobile phase mixture in the ratio of 30:70(Buffer:Acetonitrile).The HPLC separation was achieved with the column - Waters X Bridge, C18,4.6x250mm, 5 μ m diameter. The response was recorded at the 254nm using UV detector without any interference and the runtime was 15mins.The Auto sampler temperature was maintained at 5°C.The injection volume was about10 μ Latthe flow rate of 1.0mL/min .The method was developed with the reference of ICH guidelines for Analytical Method Validation Q2 (R2),USP 40< 1225> Validation of compendia Methods,USP40<1226>Verification of compendia Methods .The method was successfully applied for the determination of assay of Chlorpromazine Active Pharmaceutical ingredient.

This proposed method can be optimized and

applied for the determination of assay of Chlorpromazine Active Pharmaceutical ingredient at less time and at low cost.

REFERENCES:

1. The Merck Index, Merck Research Laboratoires, U.S.A 2006 ; 14thed. pp1573, 598 927.
2. Indian pharmacopoeia 2007, volume 2, Government of India, ministry of health and welfare, published by The Indian pharmacopoeia commission, Ghaziabad, page No. 658,1156 , 453.
3. British Pharmacopoeia, the Stationary Office, British Pharmacopoeia Commission, UK, 2009, Volume I and II, 3407.
4. United States of Pharmacopoeia, United States Pharmacopoeial Convention, Rockville, MD, 2009, Volume II, 2447.
5. Sharma BK. Instrumental methods of chemical analysis, Introduction to Analytical chemistry, 2004, 23rdedition, Goal Publishing House Meerut.
6. H.H. Willard, L.L. Merritt, J.A. Dean, F.A.

- Settle. Instrumental Methods of Analysis, 7th edition, CBS publishers and Distributors, New Delhi. 1986, PP518- 521, 580-610.
7. John Adamovics. Chromatographic Analysis of Pharmaceutical, Marcel Dekker Inc. New York, II Ed, PP74, 5-15.
 8. Gurdeep Chatwal, Sahm K. Anand. Instrumental methods of Chemical Analysis, 5th edition, Himalaya publishing house, New Delhi, 2002, PP1.1-1.8, 2.566- 2.570.
 9. D.A.Skoog,J.Holler,T.A.Nieman.PrincipleofInstrumentalAnalysis,1998,5thedition, Saunders College Publishing, PP 778-787.
 10. William Kemp. Organic Spectroscopy, Palgrave, New York, 2005, PP7-10, 328- 330.
 11. P.D Sethi. HPLC: Quantitative Analysis Pharmaceutical Formulations, CBS Publishers and distributors, New Delhi (India), 2001, PP 3 – 137.
 12. Michael E, ScharzIS, Krull. Analytical method development and Validation. 2004. PP 25-46.
 13. R. Snyder, J. Kirkland, L. Glajch. Practical HPLC method development, 1997, II Ed, A Wiley International publication, PP 235,266-268,351-353.653-600.686- 695.
 14. Method validation guidelines International Conference on harmonization; GENEVA; 1996.
 15. Analysis Profile of Drug lamivudine, Auxiliary Information-Staff Liasison: Behnam Davani, Ph, D.Expert Committee (PA7) USP28-NFile23 Page 1106.Pharmacopiea Forum: Volume no.30 (3) Page 881.
 16. Analysis Profile of Drugs Substances, Lamivudine Drug Bank (DB00709).Tenofovir Drug Bank (BD00300) Efavirenz Drug Bank (DB00625).
 17. María Segunda Aurora Prado Department of Pharmacy, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Sao Paulo, S ~ ao Paulo, Brazil.
 18. Vijay Swaroop Singh G Department of Chemistry, Noble College, Machilipatnam – 521 001. AP, INDIA Email: *vijayssgaddala@gmail.com mobile: 9848240030
Received: 25.06.18, Revised: 14.08.18, Accepted: 15.09.18
 19. N Appala Raju and Shabana Begum Simultaneous RP-HPLC Method for the Estimation of the Emtricitabine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumerate and Efavirenz in Tablet Dosage Forms Research J. Pharm. and Tech.1(4): Oct.-Dec.
 20. K Anand Babu, B Jaykar; Analytical Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Zidovudine, Lamivudine and Nevirapine Tablet by RP-HPLC, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development, September 11, Vol 3 (7), 9-14.